

Robust Control Design and Analysis Using SCILAB for a Mass-Spring-Damper System

Authors : Yoonsoo Kim

Abstract : This paper introduces an open-source software package SCILAB, an alternative of MATLAB, which can be used for robust control design and analysis of a typical mass-spring-damper (MSD) system. Using the previously published ideas in this popular mechanical system is considered to provide another example of usefulness of SCILAB for advanced control design.

Keywords : robust control, SCILAB, mass-spring-damper (MSD), popular mechanical systems

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